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Abstract

This study examined whether cigarette smoking behavior among Bangladeshi male adults can be predicted by emotional intelligence, perceived stress, and self-esteem. A self-report questionnaire package consisting of a Personal Information Form, the Emotional Intelligence Scale, the Perceived Stress Scale, and the Self-Esteem Scale was administered to a purposive sample of 210 males aged 19 to 45 years in Dhaka city. The sample was equally distributed between smokers ($n = 105$) and non-smokers ($n = 105$). Pearson point-biserial correlation analyses revealed that smoking behavior was significantly and positively associated with perceived stress, while displaying significant negative associations with both emotional intelligence and self-esteem. Furthermore, binary logistic regression analysis demonstrated that perceived stress and self-esteem independently and significantly predict smoking behavior among the respondents. These findings provide empirical support for incorporating psychological interventions, particularly stress management and self-esteem enhancement, into public health anti-smoking policies.

Perceived Stress and Self-Esteem as Significant Predictors of Cigarette Smoking Behavior of Bangladeshi Male Adults

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Many previous studies have reported that smoking behavior is associated with a number of psychological variables. The present study examined whether smoking behavior of Bangladeshi adults can be predicted from their emotional intelligence, perceived stress, and self-esteem. A self-report questionnaire package comprising of Personal Information Form, Emotional Intelligence Scale, Perceived Stress Scale, and Self-Esteem Scale was administered on a purposive sample of 210, nineteen-through 45-year-old males distributed equally to smoking and non-smoking groups to collect data. Pearson Point Biserial Correlation and Binary Logistic Regression were performed to analyze the data. The results of correlation analyses revealed that smoking behavior of the respondents was negatively associated with emotional intelligence and self-esteem and positively with perceived stress. The results of regression analysis revealed that perceived stress and self-esteem can independently and significantly predict smoking behavior of the respondents. These findings can be taken to suggest that antismoking policies should incorporate, among others, strategies for enhancing emotional intelligence, managing stress, and fostering self-esteem of individuals to help prevent or stop their smoking behavior which is the gateway to further addictive behaviors.

Key words: emotional intelligence, perceived stress, self-esteem, smoking behavior

A large body of research has documented that smoking behavior is associated with a number of psychological variables. Weiss, Mouttapa,

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Cen, Johnson, and Unger (2011) studied a culturally diverse sample of 1,771 adolescents who reported that the risk of smoking initiation was significantly higher among students who scored higher on hostility and depressive symptoms, and were bully-victims. Mykletun, Overland, Aarø, Liabø, and Stewart (2008) carried out a population-based health survey on 60,814 adults aged between 20 to 89 years and reported that anxiety and depression were the most common in current smokers followed by quitters, and then never-smokers. Siahpush, Borland, and Scollo (2003) found the probability of experiencing financial stress to be 1.5 - 2.0 times higher for smoking households than for non-smoking homes. Baker, Brandon, and Chassin (2004) reported that anxiety and depression may also cause smoking initiation and heavy smoking. Liu (2003) in his study on a sample of 1360 Chinese adolescents reported that smokers experienced more life stress than nonsmokers. Siqueira, Diab, Bodian, and Rolnitzky (2000) based on a study on a population of 954 clinic patients aged between 12 to 21 years reported that negative life events, perceived stress, greater use of the negative coping methods of anger and helplessness, and the use of the positive coping methods of parental support and cognitive coping were significantly and independently related to smoking status.

Trinidad and Johnson (2002) conducted a study on 205 multi-ethnic adolescents with a mean age of 12.63 years to explore the relationship between emotional intelligence and tobacco and alcohol use. They found emotional intelligence to be negatively correlated with a general, overall measure of tobacco and alcohol use, and with individual tobacco and alcohol scales and items. However, they suggested the need to carry out further research to validate these findings. Kim (2004) conducted a research on Korean secondary school students and reported self-esteem among other variables to have strongly related to smoking behavior of the students. Mullan and NicGabhainn (2002) in a study on 7,706 Irish young people have reported that there was no significant difference in self-esteem scores between those who had and had not tried smoking.

Tobacco use is widespread in the subcontinent including Bangladesh, India, Nepal, and Pakistan with significant differences in prevalence between male and female. The Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics in 1997 reported that smoking rates were higher among men than women; the highest reported rate was 70.3% for men aged 35–49 years, while the lowest was 0.1% for girls aged 10–14 years (cited in Efroymsen & Ahmed, 2003). Expenditure on cigarettes represents a major burden for impoverished Bangladeshis (Efroymsen, Ahmed, Townsend, et al.,

2001). An average male cigarette smokers spent more than twice as much on cigarettes as per capita expenditure on clothing, housing, health and education combined and a typical poor smoker could easily add over 500 calories to the diet of one or two children with his or her daily tobacco expenditure. Prevalence of tobacco smoking is 36% for males and 9% for females of Pakistani sample (cited in Ahmed, Rashid, McDonald, & Ahmed, 2008); 20.5% for boys and 2.9% for girls of Nepalese sample of college students (Sreeramareddy, Kishore, Paudel, & Menezes, 2008). A survey on 599 college students of Andhra Pradesh in India demonstrated that the prevalence of tobacco smoking is 48 out of 387 male students and 1 out of 212 female students (Gavarasana, Doddi, Prasad, Allam, & Murthy, 1991).

It appears from the literature discussed that stress, self-esteem, and emotional intelligence are some of the important psychological variables reported to have been associated with smoking behavior. However, the association appears inconclusive across studies. Additionally, there is no known research documented so far addressing the issue of smoking behavior in relation to those psychological variables in the cultural context of the subcontinent in general and Bangladesh in particular. Therefore, it is the objective of the present study to explore possible relations of smoking behavior of male adults of Bangladesh with their emotional intelligence, stress, and self-esteem.

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated in the present study:

1. The emotional intelligence is likely to have relationship with the probability of smoking behavior.
2. The perceived stress is likely to have relationship with the probability of smoking behavior.
3. The self-esteem is likely to have relationship with the probability of smoking behavior.

Method

Participants

The study was carried out on a sample of 210 male adults distributed equally to smokers and non-smokers. They were purposively selected from different locations in the city of Dhaka. A smoker in the present study is referred someone who reportedly had a habit of smoking three or more cigarettes per day, on a regular basis. The cigarette smokers were chosen as they constitute the vast majority of tobacco users (an estimated

70% of the tobacco produced is used for cigarettes and *bidis* - small cigarettes hand rolled in paper). Their ages ranged from 19 to 45 years. Though incidentally, this age group constitutes the largest group (more than 60%) in terms of smoking rates (cited in Efroymsen & Ahmed, 2003). The respondent's were students, service holders, or businessmen and their education varied between secondary to tertiary levels. Most of them belong to middle class and a few to lower or upper classes. The smoking and non-smoking groups matched in terms of their age, education, and socio-economic status. The distribution of the sample is presented in Table 1.

Table 1
The distribution of respondents by smoking status and occupation

Smoking status	Occupation			Total
	Student	Service	Business	
Smoker	35	35	35	105
Non-Smoker	35	35	35	105
Total	70	70	70	210

Assessment Measures

The following questionnaires along with a Personal Information Form (PIF) were used in the present study:

Emotional Intelligence Scale (EIS). The adapted Bangla version (Hossain & Uddin 2008) of the EIS scale (Hyde, Pethe, & Dhar, 2002) was used to measure emotional intelligence of the respondents in the present study. It is a 34-item 5-point scale (anchored 1 for strongly agree to 5 for strongly disagree). These items measure emotional intelligence by measuring different aspects of personality such as, self awareness, empathy, self motivation, emotional stability, managing relations, integrity, self development, value orientation, commitment, altruistic behavior. High score indicates high level of emotional intelligence. The Cronbach alpha was 0.86 and the criterion validity was 0.75 for the Bangla version. This indicates that the Bangla version was reliable and valid.

Perceived Stress Scale (PSS). The adapted Bangla version (Fahim, 2001) of the PSS (Cohen, Kamarck, & Mermelstein, 1983) was used to measure stress of the respondents. It is a 10-item 5-point Likert type

scale. It measures the degree to which situations in one's life are appraised as stressful. Items were designed to tap how unpredictable, uncontrollable, and overloaded respondents find their lives. The scale also includes a number of direct queries about current levels of experienced stress. The questions in the PSS ask about feelings and thoughts during the last month. In each case, respondents are asked how often they felt a certain way. Responses to items 1, 2, 3, 6, 9 and 10 were given weights of 0 for 'never'; 1 for 'almost never'; 2 for 'sometimes'; 3 for 'fairly often'; and 4 for 'very often'. PSS scores were obtained by reversing responses (e.g., 0 = 4, 1 = 3, 2 = 2, 3 = 1, 4 = 0) to the four positively stated items (items 4, 5, 7, 8) and then summing across all scale items. The higher the score, the higher is the stress. The coefficient of correlation between the Bangla and the English versions of the PSS was .90 and that between two administrations of the Bangla version with an interval of 2 weeks was .94.

Rosenberg Self-Esteem Scale (SES). The Bangla translated version (Uddin & Soma, 2007) of Rosenberg's Self-Esteem Scale (Rosenberg, 1965) was used to measure self-esteem of the participants. It is a 10-item 4-point Likert type scale. The scale contains 5 positive and 5 negative items. A score of 0 is assigned to 'strongly disagree', 1 to 'disagree', 2 to 'agree', and 3 to 'strongly agree'. Negative items (2, 5, 6, 8, and 9) were reverse scored. The sum of the scores across all items was the total scale score for an individual. The higher the score the higher is the individual's self-esteem. The Cronbach Alpha observed in the present study was 0.51 for the scale.

Procedure

The second author approached students, service-holders, and businessmen in different locations of the capital city, Dhaka. He conveniently selected smokers and non-smokers from the three groups of participants. After taking consent and establishing necessary rapport with them he administered self-report measures at their working places. It took about 30 minutes to complete the questionnaires. The author thanked participants for their sincere cooperation and said goodbye to them.

Results

To comprehend the general pattern of the data, we calculated the descriptive statistics for emotional intelligence, perceived stress, and self-esteem of smokers and non-smokers. The results are presented in Table 2.

It is evident from the table that the respondents who smoke cigarettes presented lower level emotional intelligence, higher level perceived stress, and lower self-esteem than who do not smoke.

Table 2

Descriptive statistics for emotional intelligence, perceived stress, and self-esteem of smokers and non-smokers

Variables	Smokers' Replies		Non-smokers' Replies		Possible Scores		
	M	SD	M	SD	Lowest	Highest	Midpoint
Emotional intelligence	111.24	13.97	120.70	12.25	34	170	102
Perceived stress	21.85	5.29	17.42	5.03	0	40	20
Self-esteem	16.02	5.14	20.46	4.53	0	30	15

To test whether the differences between smokers and non-smokers were significant, we employed inferential statistics. Since *smoking status* is a categorical variable (a true dichotomy in the present study; non-smoker was coded as '0' and smoker as '1') and emotional intelligence, perceived stress, and self-esteem are continuous variables, we calculated Pearson point biserial correlation. The results showed that emotional intelligence, perceived stress, and self-esteem were significantly correlated with smoking status ($r = .39, p < .01$; $r = -.41, p < .01$; $r = -.34, p < .01$, respectively). Smokers scored significantly lower on emotional intelligence, higher on perceived stress, and lower on self-esteem.

To test further whether emotional intelligence, perceived stress, and self-esteem can predict the likelihood that an adult male will be engaged in cigarette smoking behavior, a three-predictor binary logistic model was fitted to the data. The logistic regression analysis was performed in an SPSS for Windows environment. The results showed that, Predicted logit of (Cigarette smoking behavior) = $0.683 + (0.09) * \text{Perceived Stress} + (-0.11) * \text{Self-Esteem} + (-0.00) * \text{Emotional Intelligence}$.

According to the model, the log of the odds of an adult male being engaged in cigarette smoking behavior was positively related to perceived stress ($p < .05$), negatively related to self-esteem ($p < .05$), and negatively but insignificantly related to emotional intelligence ($p > .05$; Table 3). In other words, the higher the perceived stress score, the higher likely it is that an adult male will be engaged in cigarette smoking behavior. On the other hand, the lower the self-esteem score, the high likely it is that an adult male will be engaged in cigarette smoking

behavior. Emotional intelligence has not proved to be a significant predictor of cigarette smoking behavior, however.

Table 3 also shows that for each point increase on the emotional intelligence score, the perceived stress score, and the self-esteem score, the odds of being involved in cigarette smoking behavior decrease from 1.0 to .99, increase from 1.0 to 1.09, and decrease from 1.0 to .89, respectively. In terms of the research hypothesis posed earlier – “the likelihood that an adult male will be engaged in smoking behavior is related to his perceived stress and self-esteem scores- logistic regression results supported this proposition. Specifically, the likelihood of an adult male being engaged in smoking behavior was positively related to his perceived stress score and negatively to his self-esteem score. We reached this conclusion with multiple evidences: the significant test result of the logistic model, statistically significant test results of the predictors, and insignificant HL test of goodness-of-fit. The evidences will be presented in what follows.

In presenting the assessment of logistic regression results, it is important to include sufficient information to address these issues, (i) an overall evaluation of the logistic model, (ii), statistical tests of individual predictors, (iii), goodness-of-fit statistics, and (iv) an assessment of the predicted probabilities. The first three types of information are presented in Table 3 and the fourth in Table 4.

Table 3

Regression of smoking behavior on emotional intelligence, perceived stress, and self-esteem

Predictor	β	$SE\beta$	Wald's χ^2	df	p	e^β (odds ratio)
Emotional intelligence	-.00	.01	0.04	1	.83	.99
Perceived stress	.09	.03	5.74	1	.01	1.09
Self-esteem	-.11	.05	5.12	1	.02	.89
Constant	.68	2.06	0.10	1	.74	1.98
Test			χ^2	df	P	
Overall model evaluation						
Likelihood ratio test			41.91	3	.001	
Goodness-of-fit test						
Hosmer & Lemeshow			3.66	8	.88	

Note. Alpha = 0.05 level, Cox & Snell $R^2 = .19$, Nagelkerke $R^2 = .26$

Overall model evaluation

A logistic model is said to provide a better fit to the data if it demonstrates an improvement over the intercept-only model (also called the null model). An intercept-only model serves as a good baseline because it contains no predictors. Consequently, according to this model, all observation would be predicted to belong in the largest outcome category. An improvement over this baseline is examined by using an inferential statistical test: the likelihood ratio test. The tests result is significant at 0.05 level that rejects the null hypothesis (all predictors have no effect on the outcome of dependent variable). This result supports the overall significance of our proposed model for outcome variable.

Statistical tests of individual predictors

The statistical significance of individual regression coefficients (i.e., β) is tested using the Wald chi-square statistic (Table 3). According to Table 3, both perceived stress and self-esteem scores were significant predictors of probability of smoking ($p < .05$). Emotional intelligence score has not achieved significance ($p > .05$), however. The test of the intercept (i.e., the constant in Table 3) merely suggests whether an intercept should be included in the model. For the present data set, the test result ($p > .05$) suggested that an alternative model without the intercept might be applied to the data.

Goodness-of-fit statistics

Goodness-of-fit statistics assess the fit of a logistic model against actual outcomes (i.e., whether an adult male is likely to be engaged in cigarette smoking behavior or not). One inferential test and two descriptive measures are presented in Table 3. The inferential goodness-of-fit test is the Hosmer-Lemeshow (H-L) test that yielded a $\chi^2(8)$ of 3.66 and was insignificant ($p > .05$), suggesting that the model fit to the data well. In other words, the null hypothesis of a good model fit to data was tenable. The H-L statistic is a Pearson chi-square statistic, calculated from a $2 \times g$ table of observed and estimated expected frequencies, where, g is the numbers of groups formed from the estimated probabilities.

Two additional descriptive measures of goodness of fit presented in Table 3 are R^2 indices, defined by Cox and Snell (1989) and Nagelkerke (1991), respectively. These indices are variations of the R^2 concept defined for the OLS regression model. None, however, renders the

meaning of variance explained (Long, 1997; Menard, 2000). For these reasons, a researcher can treat these two R^2 indices as supplementary to other, more useful evaluative indices, such as the overall evaluation of the model, tests of individual regression coefficients, and the goodness-of-fit test statistic.

Validation of predicted probabilities

SPSS output includes a classification table that documents the validity of predicted probabilities. The first two rows in Table 4 represent the two possible outcomes, and the two columns under the heading "Predicted" are for high and low probabilities, based on a cutoff point. The cutoff point is set at .50 by SPSS. According to Table 4, with the cutoff set at .50, the prediction for adults who were smoking was more accurate than that for those who were not smoking.

Table 4

The observed and the predicted frequencies for smoking status by Logistic Regression with the cutoff of 0.50

Observed	Predicted		% correct
	Yes	No	
Yes	76	29	72.4
No	33	72	68.6
Overall % correct			70.5

Note. Sensitivity = $76/(76 + 29)\% = 72.38\%$. Specificity = $72/(33+72)\% = 68.57\%$. False positive = $33/(33 + 76)\% = 30.28\%$. False negative = $29/(29 + 72)\% = 28.71\%$.

Discussion

The present study examined whether cigarette smoking behavior in adult males of Bangladesh can be predicted from their emotional intelligence, perceived stress, and self-esteem. To address these issues, three hypotheses were formulated which state that (i) the higher the emotional intelligence, the lower the probability of smoking behavior, (ii) the higher the perceived stress, the higher the probability of smoking behavior, and (iii) the higher the self-esteem, the lower the probability of smoking behavior. A binary logistic regression was performed on the data to test the hypotheses. The results provided supporting evidences for the second and the third hypotheses.

The findings of the present study could not provide supporting evidence for the first hypothesis. However, the findings are consistent with the report of past studies. Trinidad and Johnson (2002) have reported that emotional intelligence was negatively correlated with

tobacco use. We found a significant negative correlation between the variables by performing Pearson point biserial correlation on the data. The magnitude of the coefficient is moderate.

The result concerning the second hypothesis is consistent with the findings of Liu (2003) who reported that smokers experienced more life stress than nonsmokers. Similar findings have been reported by Siqueira, Diab, Bodian, and Rolnitzky (2000). A question naturally arises as to why individuals with higher perceived stress have higher probability of being engaged in cigarette smoking behavior. One possible reason might be that nicotine causes the brain to release chemicals, called neurotransmitters. Some of these chemicals, such as beta-endorphin and norepinephrine, can cause a person to feel better, but only for a short time. They can improve one's mood for a while. So, smoking can serve as a quick "pick-me-up."

The result concerning the third hypothesis is consistent with the findings of Kim (2004) who reported association of self-esteem with smoking behavior of the Korean students. The linkage between self-esteem and tobacco use can be interpreted by problem behavior theory (Jessor & Jessor, 1977) and self-derogation theory (Kandel, 1980). According to problem behavior theory, self-esteem is part of a personal belief structure composed mainly of cognitive regulatory mechanisms (i.e., social criticism, alienation, locus of control) that suppress vulnerability to engage in nonconforming behavior. Combined with additional precipitating factors such as parental tolerance for deviance, low worth of achievement and independence, and support from deviant peers, problem behavior theory posits that low self-esteem can reduce barriers to engaging in delinquent behaviors. Self-derogation theory augments this view by positing that low self-worth produces psychological distress, including a desire for greater self-acceptance, which can encourage some youth to distance themselves from conventional groups in an effort to find alternative sources of esteem enhancement. According to self-derogation theory, once emotional ties to important socializing agents such as family and school are broken, self-derogating youth become more likely to bond with deviant peers as a means of gaining self-acceptance, thus heightening vulnerability to problem behavior.

Several limitations of this study should be noted. First, the sample was taken from a section of the country, namely Dhaka city, which differs from the rest in many respects. Second, the sample size is small that delimits generalization of the findings. Third, the data were entirely

self-report, that might have introduced the potential of confounding constructs. Cumulatively, these limitations provide some basis for caution in the interpretation of the current findings. Further research on the developmental relations between self-esteem and tobacco use is warranted in light of the overall evidence favoring a protective and beneficial role of self-esteem.

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